
Series: PHYSICS

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Schrödinger equation and the flight of electromagnetic particles

Annotation

A real (without probabilities) solution to the Schrödinger equations is given. Based on this solution, a mathematical model of the particle is created as a certain set of electromagnetic waves pulsating in a limited volume. It is shown that such a particle moves by a flow of electromagnetic energy, which is continuously generated by the pulsation of an internal electromagnetic wave. Moreover, the magnitudes of this flow and energy remain constant over time.

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1. Introduction

Unlike the Newton equation, from which the observed trajectory $r(t)$ of a material point is found, from the Schrödinger equation one finds in the general case **complex**, i.e. unobservable wave function $\psi(r, t)$. Only the module of this function is observed. Immediately after the discovery of the Schrödinger equation, Born gave a statistical interpretation of the wave function $\psi(r, t)$. Magnitude $|\psi(r, t)|$ - the intensity of the wave is interpreted as the probability density of finding a particle at point r at time t . Then the wave function $\psi(r, t)$ is the amplitude of the probability density, or simply the amplitude of the probability. The probability of a reliable event of detecting a particle somewhere in space should be equal

to one. This condition, the normalization condition, is an additional requirement for the form of the wave function.

This solution, together with the interpretation of the experiments, leads to the conclusion that $\psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ it should be considered as a synthesis of wave, corpuscular and statistical concepts of a microobject. As a result, it turns out that the principle of superposition quantum states is valid for wave functions. He $\psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is that if the system can be in states described by the wave functions ψ_1 and ψ_2 , then for any complex numbers b_1 and b_2 , where $|b_1|^2 + |b_2|^2 = 1$, it can also be in the state described by the wave function

$$\psi = b_1\psi_1 + b_2\psi_2.$$

We will not continue this story - this is a complex story written by brilliant people, and the triumphant reality of quantum mechanics. It all started with the fact that it was not possible to immediately find a real, rather than complex, solution to the Schrödinger equation.

We must look for the real solution to the equation Schrödinger. This is not the first time the author has raised this question. Batanov in [1] thoroughly considers the need to find another solution and proposes a new solution. But he failed to get rid of probabilities and in conclusion he says: "Apparently, determinism and probability are manifestations of a single duality that lies at the foundations of this world." The resulting solution denies this duality.

2. Solution of the Schrödinger equation

The Schrödinger equation has the form

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \Delta \psi + U(x, y, z, t) \quad (1)$$

where $\psi = \psi(x, y, z, t)$ is the wave function characterizing the state of an elementary particle;

$U(x, y, z, t)$ is potential energy of an elementary particle;

$\hbar$ is Planck's constant;

m is particle mass.

We will slightly change the classical form of this equation and write it in the following form

$$\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \Delta \psi + U \times \psi, \quad (2)$$

$$U = \frac{V}{v} S, \quad (2a)$$

where S is the energy flux density, v is the speed of the longitudinal movement of the particle, V is the volume of the particle. Vector multiplication is necessary to ensure that the dimensionality of physical quantities is observed in reality. We got rid of the imaginary unit, and

replaced the potential energy (as imaginary as this unit) of the particle with real energy, presenting it in the form (2a). We replaced the product of energy by a function with a vector product.

We assume that ψ is a certain quantity (similar, for example, to electrical intensity) that fluctuates in time and in the volume of the particle. The total energy flow can be represented as a vector

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} S_x \\ S_y \\ S_z \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

This flow must satisfy the law of conservation of energy for an autonomous particle, i.e.

$$S_x + S_y + S_z = \text{const}. \quad (4)$$

In this case, equation (2) can be written as:

$$\hbar \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \psi_x}{\partial t} \\ \frac{\partial \psi_y}{\partial t} \\ \frac{\partial \psi_z}{\partial t} \end{bmatrix} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 \psi_x}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_x}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_x}{\partial z^2} \\ \frac{\partial^2 \psi_y}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_y}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_y}{\partial z^2} \\ \frac{\partial^2 \psi_z}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_z}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_z}{\partial z^2} \end{bmatrix} + \frac{V}{v} \begin{bmatrix} S_x \\ S_y \\ S_z \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} \psi_x \\ \psi_y \\ \psi_z \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

We have a system of equations (4, 5) with three unknowns ψ_x, ψ_y, ψ_z . Such a system may have a real solution.

Let's find the vector product

$$\begin{bmatrix} S_x \\ S_y \\ S_z \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} \psi_x \\ \psi_y \\ \psi_z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_y \psi_z - S_z \psi_y \\ S_z \psi_x - S_x \psi_z \\ S_x \psi_y - S_y \psi_x \end{bmatrix}. \quad (6)$$

From (5, 6) we find:

$$\hbar \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \psi_x}{\partial t} \\ \frac{\partial \psi_y}{\partial t} \\ \frac{\partial \psi_z}{\partial t} \end{bmatrix} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 \psi_x}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_x}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_x}{\partial z^2} \\ \frac{\partial^2 \psi_y}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_y}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_y}{\partial z^2} \\ \frac{\partial^2 \psi_z}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_z}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_z}{\partial z^2} \end{bmatrix} + \frac{V}{v} \begin{bmatrix} S_y \psi_z - S_z \psi_y \\ S_z \psi_x - S_x \psi_z \\ S_x \psi_y - S_y \psi_x \end{bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

To find the solution we will move to cylindrical coordinates. Then, by analogy with (7), we obtain:

$$\hbar \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \psi_r}{\partial t} \\ \frac{\partial \psi_\phi}{\partial t} \\ \frac{\partial \psi_z}{\partial t} \end{bmatrix} + \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \begin{bmatrix} \left(\frac{1}{r} + r\right) \frac{\partial^2 \psi_r}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi_r}{\partial \phi^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_r}{\partial z^2} \\ \left(\frac{1}{r} + r\right) \frac{\partial^2 \psi_\phi}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi_\phi}{\partial \phi^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_\phi}{\partial z^2} \\ \left(\frac{1}{r} + r\right) \frac{\partial^2 \psi_z}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi_z}{\partial \phi^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_z}{\partial z^2} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{V}{v} \begin{bmatrix} S_\phi \psi_z - S_z \psi_\phi \\ S_z \psi_r - S_r \psi_z \\ S_r \psi_\phi - S_\phi \psi_r \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

We will look for a solution under the conditions

$$\psi_z = 0, \quad (9a)$$

$$S_r = S_\phi = 0. \quad (9b)$$

In this case, from (4) it follows:

$$S_z = \text{const.} \quad (10)$$

Then from (8) we get:

$$\hbar \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \psi_r}{\partial t} \\ \frac{\partial \psi_\phi}{\partial t} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \begin{bmatrix} \left(\frac{1}{r} + r\right) \frac{\partial^2 \psi_r}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi_r}{\partial \phi^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_r}{\partial z^2} \\ \left(\frac{1}{r} + r\right) \frac{\partial^2 \psi_\phi}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi_\phi}{\partial \phi^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_\phi}{\partial z^2} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \frac{V}{v} \begin{bmatrix} -S_z \psi_\phi \\ S_z \psi_r \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Equation (11) is a system of two equations:

$$\hbar \frac{\partial \psi_r}{\partial t} + \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left[\left(\frac{1}{r} + r\right) \frac{\partial^2 \psi_r}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi_r}{\partial \phi^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_r}{\partial z^2} \right] + \frac{V}{v} S_z \psi_\phi = 0, \quad (12)$$

$$\hbar \frac{\partial \psi_\phi}{\partial t} + \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left[\left(\frac{1}{r} + r\right) \frac{\partial^2 \psi_\phi}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi_\phi}{\partial \phi^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_\phi}{\partial z^2} \right] - \frac{V}{v} S_z \psi_r = 0. \quad (13)$$

We will look for a solution to these two equations with two unknowns ψ_ϕ , ψ_r in the following form:

$$\psi_r = e_r(r) \text{si}, \quad (14)$$

$$\psi_\phi = e_\phi(r) \text{co}, \quad (15)$$

where

$$\text{co} = \cos(\alpha\phi + \chi z + \omega t), \quad (16)$$

$$\text{si} = \sin(\alpha\phi + \chi z + \omega t) \quad (17)$$

and the constants α, χ, ω are defined. Here and are the unknown functions $e_r(r), e_\phi(r)$ of the argument r . From (12, 13, 14, 15) we find:

$$\hbar\omega e_r \text{co} + \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left[\left(\frac{1}{r} + r\right) \frac{\partial^2 e_r}{\partial r^2} - \frac{1}{r^2} \alpha^2 e_r - \chi^2 e_r \right] \text{si} + \frac{V}{v} S_z e_\phi \text{co} = 0, \quad (18)$$

$$-\hbar\omega e_\phi \text{si} + \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left[\left(\frac{1}{r} + r\right) \frac{\partial^2 e_\phi}{\partial r^2} - \frac{1}{r^2} \alpha^2 e_\phi - \chi^2 e_\phi \right] \text{co} - \frac{V}{v} S_z e_r \text{si} = 0. \quad (19)$$

It can be seen that two equations (18, 19) break down into 4 equations of the form:

$$\left(\frac{1}{r} + r\right) \frac{\partial^2 e_r}{\partial r^2} - \frac{1}{r^2} \alpha^2 e_r - \chi^2 e_r = 0, \quad (20)$$

$$\hbar\omega e_r + \frac{V}{v} S_z e_\phi = 0, \quad (21)$$

$$\left(\frac{1}{r} + r\right) \frac{\partial^2 e_\phi}{\partial r^2} - \frac{1}{r^2} \alpha^2 e_\phi - \chi^2 e_\phi = 0, \quad (22)$$

$$\hbar\omega e_\phi + \frac{V}{v} S_z e_r = 0, \quad (23)$$

From here we find:

$$e_\phi = Z e_r, \quad (24)$$

$$\hbar\omega + \frac{v}{v} S_z = 0, \quad (25)$$

where

$$Z = (0,1). \quad (25a)$$

We just have to solve equation (20). Appendix 1 shows that solving this equation reduces to solving an equation of the form

$$\ddot{e}_r - \left(\frac{1}{r}\alpha^2 + r\chi^2\right) e_r = 0. \quad (26)$$

We will write this solution in the form

$$e_r = \text{Sch}(A, r), \quad (26a)$$

where A is a constant equal to the value of the first derivative with a zero argument. This function increases from zero.

So, the real solution to the modified Schrödinger equation of the form (2) in cylindrical coordinates is a vector of the form

$$\psi = \begin{bmatrix} \psi_r \\ \psi_\varphi \\ \psi_z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} e_r(r) \text{si} \\ e_\varphi(r) \text{co} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} e_r(r) \text{si} \\ Z e_r(r) \text{co} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (27)$$

and the energy flow has a constant (time independent) value S_z .

Let us now move on to the Cartesian coordinate system, where we need to find a vector of the form

$$\psi = \begin{bmatrix} \psi_x \\ \psi_y \\ \psi_z \end{bmatrix}. \quad (28)$$

Appendix 2 shows that with known ψ , determined by (27), one can find

$$\psi_x = e_r \sin((\alpha + 1)\varphi + \chi z + \omega t), \quad (29)$$

$$\psi_y = e_r \cos((\alpha - 1)\varphi + \chi z + \omega t). \quad (30)$$

3. Electromagnetic particles

In previous works the author showed that particles are both waves and particles at the same time, and not alternately. The particle is a "wave-AND-particle", not a "wave-OR-particle". A particle represents a certain collection of electromagnetic waves and this collection has mass. Particles do not require anything other than electromagnetic waves to exist. In [2, 3, 4] it is shown that there are cubic, spherical, disk particles. Therefore, particles can be called electromagnetic. Electromagnetic waves in these particles satisfy Maxwell's equations. Next we will consider an electromagnetic particle in which electromagnetic waves satisfy the Schrödinger equation.

It was shown above that the solution to the Schrödinger equation for a particle is a wave with vector (2.27). We can assume that this is the vector of electrical intensity

$$E = \begin{bmatrix} E_r \\ E_\varphi \\ E_z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} e_r(r) \text{si} \\ Z_e e_r(r) \text{co} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

Let us assume that there is another vector in the same particle

$$H = \begin{bmatrix} H_r \\ H_\varphi \\ H_z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} h_r(r) \text{co} \\ Z_h h_r(r) \text{si} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

which is a solution to another Schrödinger equation in the form

$$h_r(r) = \text{Sch}(B, r), \quad (2a)$$

where B is a constant equal to the value of the first derivative with a zero argument. We can assume that this is the vector of magnetic intensity. The mass, frequency, speed and energy flow common to these equations allows us to state that we have obtained a wave-AND-particle, in which the electromagnetic wave satisfies two Schrödinger equations. For definitions (1, 2) we will fulfill the condition

$$Z_h = -Z_e, \quad (3)$$

those. To determine the electric and magnetic intensities, we will use different Schrödinger equations - we will call them different-signed.

Let us find the particle energy flux density using the Poynting equation:

$$S = E \times H \quad (3)$$

or

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} S_r \\ S_\varphi \\ S_z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} E_\varphi H_z - E_z H_\varphi \\ E_z H_r - E_r H_z \\ E_r H_\varphi - E_\varphi H_r \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

Combining this formula with (1, 2), we find that

$$S_r = S_\varphi = 0. \quad (5)$$

We obtained formula (2.9c), the validity of which was assumed earlier. Next we find:

$$S_z = E_r H_\varphi - E_\varphi H_r \quad (6)$$

or, taking into account (1, 2),

$$S_z = e_r \text{si} Z_h h_r \text{si} - Z_e e_r \text{si} h_r \text{si} \quad (7)$$

or, taking into account (3),

$$S = -Z_e (e_r h_r \text{si}^2 + e_r h_r \text{co}^2) \quad (8)$$

or

$$S = -Z_e e_r h_r. \quad (9)$$

We have shown that condition (2.10), the validity of which was assumed earlier, is satisfied: the flow of electromagnetic energy remains constant over time.

Let's also find the speed of the particle. Obviously, this speed is equal to the derivative $\frac{dz}{dt}$ of the function $z(t)$ given implicitly in the form (2.16, 2.17). Consider, for example, function (2.16). We have:

$$\frac{d(\text{co})}{dz} = \frac{d}{dz} (\cos(\alpha\varphi + \chi z + \omega t)) = -\text{si} \cdot \chi, \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{d(\text{co})}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} (\cos(\alpha\varphi + \chi z + \omega t)) = -\text{si} \cdot \omega. \quad (11)$$

Then the speed of propagation of a monochromatic electromagnetic wave

$$v = \frac{dz}{dt} = \frac{d(\text{co})}{dt} / \frac{d(\text{co})}{dz} = \frac{\omega}{\chi}. \quad (12)$$

4. Discussion

We have obtained a mathematical model of an electromagnetic particle in the form of two different-sign modified Schrödinger equations. – we will call them. Two physical objects can be considered:

1. electromagnetic wave as an extended object, the movement of which is described by Maxwell's equations, and the speed of propagation is equal to the speed of light;
2. electromagnetic particle, "made" of an electromagnetic wave pulsating in a limited volume, the movement of which (particles) with a certain (arbitrary) speed is described by two Schrödinger equations.

An electromagnetic particle, when pulsating an internal electromagnetic wave, continuously generates a flow of electromagnetic energy that moves like a particle. In this case, the electromagnetic energy of the particle remains constant (as well as the energy flow).

The mass m included in the Schrödinger formula is created by the electromagnetic field. Therefore, following J. J. Thompson [5], we will call this mass the electromagnetic mass of the particle and define it by the formula

$$m = U/v^2 \quad (1)$$

where v is the speed of the particle or, which is the same thing, the speed $v = c$ of the movement of electromagnetic energy relative to the particle. The energy U is also kinetic energy and therefore this mass can be called the inertial mass of the particle. The particle moves by inertia, possessing this inertial mass (with its own fuel-free engine "on board").

The author does not claim any novelty in the interpretation of the relationship between mass and energy: at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries, numerous variants were proposed and experimentally confirmed [5]. But further, formula (1) will be derived more rigorously. This means that the Schrödinger equation allows us to justify the calculation of electromagnetic mass using the formula (1).

All characteristics of this self-propelled particle are determined by its volume and parameters α, χ, ω .

Let's compare the resulting solution and the solution to Maxwell's equations for a cylindrical wave in a vacuum [5, Chapter 1] - see, table. 1, where the first column shows trigonometric functions of tensions of a form common to both solutions, and the following columns show the amplitudes of these functions.

Table 1/

	Шрёдингер	Максвелл
$E_r = e_r(r)\text{si}$	$e_r = \text{Sch}(A, r)$	$e_r = Ar^{\alpha-1}$
$E_\varphi = e_\varphi(r)\text{co}$	$e_\varphi = Z_e e_r$	$e_\varphi = e_r$
$E_z = 0$	0	0
$H_r = h_r(r)\text{co}$	$h_r = \text{Sch}(B, r)$	$h_r = -\sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} e_r$
$H_\varphi = h_\varphi(r)\text{si}$	$h_\varphi = -Z_e h_r$	$h_\varphi = -h_r$
$H_z = 0$	0	0
χ	не определено	$\omega\sqrt{\mu\varepsilon}$
$S = -Z_e e_r h_r$	$-Z_e \text{Sch}(A, r)\text{Sch}(B, r)$	$-\sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} e_r^2$

Моделирование (см. приложение 1) показывает, что при $r \rightarrow 0$ функция $\text{Sch}(A, r) \rightarrow Ar$. Кроме того, при

$$r \rightarrow 0, \alpha = 2 \tag{2}$$

функция $Ar^{\alpha-1} \rightarrow Ar$. Таким образом, при выполнении условия (2) имеем:

$$\text{Sch}(A, r) = Ar^{\alpha-1} = Ar. \tag{3}$$

Аналогично,

$$\text{Sch}(B, r) = Br^{\alpha-1} = Br. \tag{4}$$

При сравнении (3, 4) и формул табл. 1 находим, что при $Z_e = 1$ для уравнений Шрёдингера и Максвелла решения совпадают и имеют

вид, показанный в правом столбце. Отличия могут быть только в значении коэффициента χ . Wherein

$$B = A \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} \quad (5)$$

Можно заметить, что при условии (5) и

$$\alpha = 2 \quad (6)$$

решения уравнений Шредингера и Максвелла полностью совпадают. В этом случае можно утверждать, что уравнение Шредингера является следствием системы уравнений Максвелла в вакууме

Следовательно, если частица движется со скоростью электромагнитной волны, частица является частью волны).

Надо отметить, что в среде (отличной от вакуума) электромагнитная частица тоже является электромагнитной волной, но может двигаться с любой скоростью. Для такой частицы предыдущий вывод не применим.

Из уравнения Шредингера следует, что волна в вакууме расходует энергию – ту энергию U , которая вносится в торец частицы и определена формулой (2.2a). При

$$Z_e = -1 \quad (7)$$

из (3-6) и табл. 1 находим плотность потока энергии:

$$S = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} e_r^2 \text{Sch}(A, r) \text{Sch}(B, r) = A^2 r^2 \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}}. \quad (8)$$

Мы показали, что выполняется условие (2.10), справедливость которого предположили ранее: поток электромагнитной энергии остается постоянным во времени.

Полный поток волны-частицы

$$\bar{S} = \int_r S dr \quad (9)$$

где интеграл берется по площади Q сечения волны-частицы. Например, если сечением является круг с радиусом R , то

$$\bar{S} = A^2 \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} \int_0^R r^2 2\pi r dr = \frac{\pi R^4}{2} A^2 \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}}. \quad (10)$$

Средняя плотность потока энергии

$$S = \bar{S} / \pi R^2 = \frac{R^2}{2} A^2 \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}}. \quad (11)$$

При известной энергии U из (2.2a, 11) можно найти коэффициент A :

$$U = \frac{v R^2}{v} A^2 \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}}, \quad (12)$$

или

$$A^2 \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} = \frac{2vU}{VR^2}, \quad (13)$$

Найдем плотность массы по формуле

$$m = \frac{S}{v^3} = \frac{1}{v^3} \frac{R^2}{2} A^2 \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} = \frac{1}{v^3} \frac{R^2}{2} \frac{2vU}{VR^2} = \frac{1}{v^2} \frac{U}{V}. \quad (14)$$

Отсюда следует известная формула, связывающая массу и энергию частица:

$$M = \frac{U}{v^2}. \quad (15)$$

Appendix 1

Let's transform equation (2.20):

$$(r + r^3)\ddot{y} - (\alpha^2 + r^2\chi^2)y = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$\ddot{y} - \frac{(\frac{1}{r}\alpha^2 + r\chi^2)}{(1+r^2)}y = 0. \quad (2)$$

For small ones we have: r

$$\ddot{y} - \left(\frac{1}{r}\alpha^2 + r\chi^2\right)y = 0. \quad (3)$$

We will denote the solution to the Schrödinger equation as

$$y = \text{Sch}(A, r), \quad (4)$$

where A is a constant equal to the value of the first derivative with a zero argument.

Fig. 1.

На рис. 1 показаны графики функций $y, y = y_1, \ddot{y} = y_2$. Показана также зеленым пунктиром функция

$$z = Ar^{\alpha-1}. \quad (5)$$

Эти функции вычисляются при следующих условиях:

$$\alpha = 2.00001, \chi = 1000, A = 3, r = [0,1, \dots 99] \cdot 10^{-6}. \quad (6)$$

Appendix 2

It is known that

$$r = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}, \quad (1)$$

$$\varphi = \text{arctg}(y/x). \quad (2)$$

At

$$e_\varphi = e_r \quad (3)$$

let's find:

$$\begin{aligned} E_x &= E_r \cos(\varphi) + E_\varphi \sin(\varphi) = e_r \text{si} \cdot \cos(\varphi) + e_\varphi \text{co} \cdot \sin(\varphi) \\ &= e_r (\text{si} \cdot \cos(\varphi) + \text{co} \cdot \sin(\varphi)) \end{aligned}$$

or

$$E_x = e_r \sin((\alpha + 1)\varphi + \chi z + \omega t), \quad (4)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} E_y &= E_r \sin(\varphi) + E_\varphi \cos(\varphi) = e_r \text{si} \cdot \sin(\varphi) + e_\varphi \text{co} \cdot \cos(\varphi) \\ &= e_r (\text{si} \cdot \sin(\varphi) + \text{co} \cdot \cos(\varphi)) \end{aligned}$$

or

$$E_y = e_r \cos((\alpha - 1)\varphi + \chi z + \omega t), \quad (5)$$

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